

Alliance Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum

Meeting Summary – 28th January 2025

Introduction

The UK Health Data Research Alliance (the Alliance) convened its fourth Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum on 28th January 2025. The meeting was co-chaired by Dr Macey Murray (Senior Research Fellow in Trial Conduct Methodology, University College London) and Associate Professor Fiona Lugg-Widger (Deputy Director of Data, Centre for Trials Research, Cardiff University). The session was attended by a diverse group of stakeholders, including clinical trialists, regulatory bodies, data custodians, funding organisations, clinicians, and academic researchers.

Key Themes and Objectives

The meeting covered several important topics, with a particular focus on:

- The Sudlow Review and its relevance to data access for trials.
- Updates from the Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group, including the recent HDR UK Frontiers meeting.
- Progress on the working group recommendations paper regarding data access for clinical trials.
- Structured discussions on three key recommendations to improve data access for trials:
 - Establishing an overarching, objective standard for assessing consent categories.
 - Creating a centralised data access approval system.
 - Developing a preset approval (precedent) pathway for commonly used datasets in trials for specific outcomes.

Sudlow Review – Trials Perspective

Dr Macey Murray presented a summary of the Sudlow Review, which was commissioned by the Chief Medical Officer for England, the UK National Statistician, and NHS England's National Director for Transformation. The review, published in November 2024, mapped linkable health datasets across the UK, identified barriers to data sharing for public benefit, and provided recommendations for overcoming these challenges.

Key issues highlighted from a clinical trials perspective included:

- The need for improved data linkage, and better knowledge around data quality, provenance/integrity, and transparency around consent.
- The recommendation for publicly funded health data infrastructure including a national health data service to enhance data access across England, and ultimately the UK.
- The establishment of a national system of GP data which will allow more complete follow-up of trial participants.

Dr Murray emphasised that the recommendations from the Sudlow Review align closely with the Forum's objectives and ongoing work to streamline data access for trials. She also highlighted that Prof Sudlow is advising the UK government as it develops the Sector Plan for Life Sciences (part of the Industrial Strategy) and the 10-year Health Plan, both to be published in Spring 2025.

Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group

Rachel Brophy provided an update on the work of the Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group, which aims to harmonise and streamline data governance processes across the UK.

Key initiatives presented:

- Development of transparency standards for data access processes, supported by funding calls to encourage adoption.
- The creation of a standardised legal toolkit for contracting data access agreements, addressing delays caused by varied and complex contractual requirements.
- A visual mapping of data access routes (referred to as the "tube map"), demonstrating the complexity of current processes and the need for greater standardisation.
- The launch of the "GUARDS" (Guided, Understandable, Aligned, Responsible, Deliver and Stewardship) principles, which aim to establish a high-level governance framework complementing the existing Five Safes model.

Attendees acknowledged the importance of this work and discussed how it aligns with the forum's priorities, particularly in relation to improving the efficiency of trial data access approvals.

Breakout Discussions: Key Recommendations for Data Access Improvements

Participants engaged in breakout discussions focused on three key recommendations:

1. Overarching, Objective Standard for Consent Categories

Current Challenges and Confusions:

- Variation in how data custodians assess the adequacy of consent is causing inconsistencies and delays.

- Historically obtained consent may not reference modern requirements for remote data linkage, causing uncertainty.
- Differences in standards for consent renewal and modification over time, particularly in longitudinal studies.
- Public confusion over consent scope, expectations for automatic NHS dataset linkage, and how to verify their own consent choices.
- The impact of evolving guidelines leading to misalignment between historical consent and current data governance frameworks.

Requirements for a Standardised Approach:

- Clear guidance on appropriate levels of consent granularity to avoid being too broad or restrictive.
- Regular updates to consent frameworks, incorporating public input to maintain transparency and trust.
- Standardisation of wording across data custodians to ensure clarity and consistency for participants.
- A significant, visible public presence (e.g., citizen panels) to build trust and ensure ongoing consultation.
- A defined process for communicating where data will be used in the future and what participants can expect regarding data sharing.
- Inclusion of national curriculum engagement to improve public understanding of data access and governance.
- Strong emphasis on transparency, including clear updates on how data is used and its benefits to research and the wider public.

2. Centralised Data Access Approval System

Functions and Responsibilities:

- A national body should ensure data access requests are processed for the right reasons and that research aligns with public health priorities.
- It should provide a structured and efficient process for navigating approvals, including REC and HRA submissions, to avoid duplication.
- Standardisation of applications, similar to an IRAS equivalent form, would simplify and expedite approval processes.
- A transparent and accountable assessment framework for research organisations to confirm their appropriateness for handling sensitive health data.
- Implementation of synthetic datasets to support researchers in defining their data requirements before submitting access requests.

- Establishment of preset approval pathways for frequently requested datasets to reduce administrative burden.

3. Precedent set Pathway for Common Datasets

Key Datasets and Trial Purposes:

- Mortality data, hospital admissions, critical care outcomes, and length of stay were highlighted as key datasets that would benefit from precedent set pathways.
- Disease-specific registries, such as the National Disease Registration Service (NDRS) for cancer trials, were identified as a priority for streamlining access.
- Inclusion of condition-specific outcomes (e.g., IBD, CVD, diabetes) was recommended to align with core outcome sets.

Ensuring Flexibility and Avoiding Bias:

- Strong governance mechanisms are needed to prevent a shift towards reliance solely on precedent set datasets, potentially restricting broader research efforts.
- Regular review of pathways, with ongoing consultation with trialists, data custodians, and patient representatives, is necessary to adapt to evolving research needs.
- Transparency and patient communication were highlighted as critical to prevent misunderstanding and potential data withdrawals.
- Monitoring and auditing through data use registers would ensure balanced use of precedent set pathways and mitigate any risk of bias.

Next Steps

- The working group will continue refining the recommendations paper, incorporating feedback from the forum discussions.
- Additional stakeholder engagement, particularly with data custodians and funders, will be sought to ensure the recommendations are feasible and implementable.
- The next forum meeting is expected to take place in May 2025, with a revised version of the recommendations paper to be shared in February for further input.
- Attendees were encouraged to express interest in joining the working group to contribute to the next phase of work.

Appendix

Contributing Organisations
Cardiff University
Health Data Research UK (HDR UK), including patient and public representatives
Health Research Authority (HRA)
Imperial College London
Intensive Care National Audit & Research Centre (ICNARC)
King's College London (KCL)
Medical Research Council (MRC), UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)
Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)
National Disease Registration Service (NDRS)
NHS England
Our Future Health
Understanding Patient Data
University College London (UCL)
University of Dundee
University of Edinburgh